

Abstract No: (IFET/EN/2025/015)

OPTIMIZING CARBON SOURCES AND HYDRAULIC RETENTION TIME FOR NITRATE REMOVAL IN WOODCHIP DENITRIFICATION BEDS

H.M.I. Thilakarathna^{1*}, D.T. Udagedara¹

¹*Department of Applied Earth Sciences, Uva Wellassa University, Badulla, Sri Lanka*

**Corresponding Author E-mail: mrt20031@std.uwu.ac.lk*

Excess nitrate (NO_3^-) from agricultural runoff is a major cause of water pollution, leading to eutrophication, poor water quality, and risks to aquatic life and human health. Addressing this issue is essential for sustainable water management and environmentally responsible farming. This study investigates how different carbon sources, concentrations, and hydraulic retention times (HRT) influence nitrate removal efficiency in woodchip denitrification beds (WDBs). Batch experiments were conducted using a laboratory-scale column system filled with woodchips and supplemented with three external carbon sources as glucose ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6$), acetic acid (CH_3COOH), and ethanol ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$) at two concentrations (5 ppm and 10 ppm) under two HRTs (24 h and 48 h). NO_3^- removal performance was evaluated by monitoring the NO_3^- and dissolved oxygen (DO) in influent and effluent samples. Results showed that $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ provided the highest NO_3^- removal rates among all treatments. At 24 h HRT, $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ achieved an average NO_3^- removal efficiency of 98.62% at 5 ppm and 94.25% at 10 ppm, compared to CH_3COOH (95.77%) and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6$ (96.33%). DO concentration decreased steadily during denitrification, creating favorable conditions for microbial activity. These findings demonstrate that $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ is an effective carbon source for enhancing NO_3^- removal in WDBs, especially at shorter HRTs. The results provide practical guidance for improving denitrification performance, supporting sustainable agricultural water treatment and contributing to cleaner, climate-resilient water management systems.

Keywords: Denitrification, Woodchip bioreactor, Nitrate removal, Agricultural water, Hydraulic retention time